

DETECTION OF SPELLING ERRORS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE USING THE MBERT MODEL

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Abstract. *This article investigates the detection of spelling errors in Uzbek-language texts using the multilingual BERT model. The study addresses the lack of effective spell-checking tools for Uzbek, unlike widely available systems for English. Due to the agglutinative structure of Uzbek, the use of both Latin and Cyrillic scripts, apostrophe variations, transliterated forms, and the limited availability of annotated corpora, automatic error detection remains a complex task. To solve this problem, a dataset of 65,534 verified Uzbek sentences was compiled from literary works, electronic documents, and online sources. Artificial spelling errors were generated, and each token was labeled as correct or erroneous. The mBERT model was fine-tuned for token-level binary classification using standard evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Experimental results showed that the proposed model achieved 94% accuracy, demonstrating its practical effectiveness for Uzbek spelling error detection and future NLP applications.*

Keywords: *e-documents, spelling errors, mBert, uzbek language, spelling detection systems.*

Introduction

Nowadays, due to the rapid development of information technologies, the volume of textual documents in various languages has been increasing significantly. According to data from the International Data Corporation (IDC), the global volume of generated digital data is expected to exceed 221 zettabytes by 2026 [1]. Furthermore, the problem of detecting and correcting spelling errors in texts is considered crucial for ensuring the accurate and comprehensible delivery of information as well as for improving the effectiveness of Natural Language Processing (NLP) systems.

The task of automatically detecting and correcting spelling errors in the Uzbek language is characterized by a number of linguistic and technological complexities. In particular, due to the agglutinative nature of the Uzbek language, hundreds of different word forms can be generated from a single root. This significantly complicates the process of covering all possible word variants during spelling error detection. Furthermore, the parallel use of both Latin and Cyrillic scripts in Uzbek, variations in the representation of apostrophe characters, and the widespread occurrence of transliterated and dialect-specific forms in informal texts reduce the accuracy of automatic spell-checking systems. In addition, the limited availability of annotated corpora and dedicated spelling error datasets for the Uzbek language poses a serious challenge for effectively training machine learning-based models.

Therefore, the development of approaches for detecting and correcting spelling errors in Uzbek texts that take into account the language-specific characteristics and are based on modern machine learning algorithms represents a relevant scientific and practical challenge. This study is

specifically aimed at addressing this issue and seeks to develop an effective and accurate spell-checking model for Uzbek-language texts.

Literature Review

The task of detecting and correcting spelling errors in texts is one of the important research directions in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP), and various approaches have been developed to address this problem.

Early spell-checking systems relied primarily on dictionaries and grammatical rules. The *Spell* program, developed for the Unix environment, is considered one of the earliest and most effective rule-based systems designed for spelling error detection [2]. This system processes an entire document as input and checks each word against a dictionary containing 25,000 words adapted for technical texts. Words not found in the dictionary are identified as spelling errors and presented to the user in the form of a list. Chaabi and Ataa Allah developed a spell-checking system for the Amazigh language by combining the full Damerau–Levenshtein distance and n-gram approaches, achieving F-measure results ranging from 86.62% to 98.74% in error detection [3]. Similarly, studies on the Bangla language reported that a combination of edit distance and n-gram models achieved an average accuracy of 96% [4]. The HINDIA model, proposed by Singh and colleagues for Hindi spelling error detection, employed an attention-based BiRNN-LSTM architecture and demonstrated high accuracy performance [5].

In a study conducted for the Assamese language, the LSTM model achieved an error detection accuracy of 92.72%, while the BiLSTM model reached 94.59% [6]. For the Tamil language, the DDSpell system developed by Uthayamoorthy et al. utilized a corpus of four million words and combined bi-gram similarity matching, minimum edit distance, and word frequency techniques [7].

For the Kannada language, Ramaneedi et al. employed the mT5 model and succeeded in reducing textual noise by 12% [8]. The introduction of Transformer architectures marked a new stage in the field of spelling correction. Models such as BERT, RoBERTa, T5, NeuSpell, and SpellBERT have demonstrated high effectiveness in detecting context-dependent spelling errors. In Chinese spelling correction studies, SpellBERT and MDCSpell models were shown to outperform baseline methods [9]. For Arabic, AraSpell has been proposed as an efficient Transformer-based model for spelling correction [10].

Methodology

The proposed methodology consists of three stages: data preprocessing, model implementation, and evaluation of the results.

Figure-1. Methodologies steps

Dataset

Within the scope of this study, a comprehensive dataset based on Uzbek-language texts was constructed. The data were collected from two primary sources:

1. Grammatically correct literary works and electronic documents;
2. News articles and textual content obtained from online resources.

The process of collecting online data was carried out using web scraping technology. The final dataset consisted of 65,534 sentences, providing a sufficient volume of data for model training.

```

[{"text": "Yani ota va onaga yaxshi muomalada bo'ling ularga aziyat etkazmang dillarini og'ritmang"}
{"text": "Ular Muso alayhissalomni bola qilib oldilar"}
{"text": "Yuragi qattiqroq sanchganda beixtiyor oyijon"}
{"text": "Qari ona to'liqlinlandi shekilli gapirolmay qoldi O'g'lim olamdan o'tgan edi o'rniga Alloh menga yangi o'g'il jo'natayotgan ekan qadaming qutlug' bo'lsin o'g'lim qizginamni bag'ringga bosib ehtiyot qilib yur deb so'zini oxiriga yetkazolmay yig'lab yig'lab rayhonli hovliga kirib ketdi"}
{"text": "Dunyodagi odamlar xalqlar va millatlar ana shu oilladan tarqalgan ekan"}
{"text": "Adangizning jahli tez bo'lgani bilan ko'ngli bo'sh"}
{"text": "O'g'lingiz ko'z ochmagan yigit bo'lsa"}
{"text": "Teztez o'ray boshladi"}
{"text": "O'sha yillarda yaratilgan adabiy asarlar orasidan bironta bolalarga bag'ishlangan durustroq asar topol madim"}
{"text": "So'zga chiqqanlarni to'liqlinlab tabrik aytayotganlar ni Beksulton tanishtirib turibdi"}
{"text": "Va erda buzg'unchilik qilib sanqib yurmanglar"}
{"text": "Nihoyat o'ylga berilgan qobil bobo boshini ilkis ko'tardi endi yuzko'z ifodalarda g'ussa tashvish kamroq edi"}
{"text": "Sog'inishmi sog'inib ko'rishganda o'zini yo'qotib qo'yishmi"}
{"text": "Yani ha albatta"}
  
```

Figure-2. Dataset example

For the error detection task, each word was assigned token-level labels: **ERR** (error) and **O** (correct).

```

{"tokens": ["Bogmi", "Zog'on", "har", "kungiday", "sohona", "dabdabasi", "bilan", "yashaydi"], "labels": ["ERR", "O", "O", "O", "ERR", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O"], "original": ["Bog'i", "Zog'on", "har", "kungiday", "shohona", "dabdabasi", "bilan", "yashaydi"]}
{"tokens": ["Nuqul", "bitta", "gapni", "qaytaradi", "Buvanga", "jabr", "bo'ldi", "bolam", "buvangga", "jabr", "bo'ldi"], "labels": ["O", "O", "O", "O", "ERR", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O"], "original": ["Nuqul", "bitta", "gapni", "qaytaradi", "Buvangga", "jabr", "bo'ldi", "bolam", "buvangga", "jabr", "bo'ldi"]}
{"tokens": ["Quvurlarning", "narxini", "Toshkentdan", "bilib", "kelisga", "qaror", "qildik"], "labels": ["O", "O", "O", "O", "ERR", "O", "O", "O"], "original": ["Quvurlarning", "narxini", "Toshkentdan", "bilib", "kelisga", "qaror", "qildik"]}
{"tokens": ["Boshqa", "bir", "nazariyaga", "ko'ra", "koinot", "yagona", "nuqtaga", "siqilgach", "yfungi", "Buyuk", "portlash", "orqali", "yana", "qayta", "tug'ilishi", "mumkin"], "labels": ["O", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O", "ERR", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O"], "original": ["Boshqa", "bir", "nazariyaga", "ko'ra", "koinot", "yagona", "nuqtaga", "siqilgach", "yangi", "Buyuk", "portlash", "orqali", "yana", "qayta", "tug'ilishi", "mumkin"]}
{"tokens": ["Panfshanba", "namozi", "digar", "Xoja", "Seron", "va", "Borno", "va", "Domani", "Ko'hning", "sayrig'a", "otlandim"], "labels": ["ERR", "O", "O", "O", "O", "ERR", "O", "O", "O", "O", "O"], "original": ["Panjshanba", "namozi", "digar", "Xoja", "Seron", "va", "Boron", "va", "Domani", "Ko'hning", "sayrig'a", "otlandim"]}
  
```

Figure-3. Dataset for training

Data preprocessing

Since the collected texts were initially in raw form, they were processed through several stages and transformed into a format suitable for model training.

In the first stage, all texts were merged into a unified corpus, and unnecessary symbols, HTML tags, and noisy elements were removed. In the next stage, the texts were segmented into sentences, excessively short and semantically insignificant sentences were excluded from the dataset, and duplicate sentences were filtered out. These steps were performed to improve dataset quality and enhance the model's generalization capability.

Subsequently, artificial spelling errors were generated to train the spelling error detection model. In this process, spelling patterns specific to the Uzbek language were modeled, including:

- substitution of phonetically similar characters ($o' \rightarrow o, g' \rightarrow g$);
- omission of characters;
- insertion of additional characters;
- transposition of neighboring characters;
- errors related to suffix usage.

As a result, both erroneous and correct variants were created for each sentence, and token-level annotation was performed. Each token was labeled either as “O” (correct) or “ERR” (error).

In the final stage, the data were transformed into a format compatible with the model. During tokenization, texts were segmented into individual words and converted into numerical representations using the tokenizer of the mBERT model. Consequently, a cleaned, structurally organized, and annotated dataset was obtained. This dataset served as the primary source of information for training and evaluating the spelling error detection model.

mBERT-Based Spelling Error Detection Model

In this study, the following approach was employed for spelling error detection. The task of identifying spelling errors was formulated as a token classification problem. For this purpose, the mBERT model, built upon the **bert-base-multilingual-cased** architecture, was utilized. This model is based on the Transformer architecture and enables deep learning of contextual relationships among words within a text. The mBERT model was pre-trained on large-scale multilingual corpora and has demonstrated effective performance across various languages, including Uzbek.

The model architecture is based on tokenizing the input text and generating contextualized vector representations for each token. Through these vector representations, the model identifies the semantic and syntactic role of each token within the sentence. One of the major advantages of the mBERT model is that it analyzes each word not in isolation but within the context of the entire sentence. This capability plays a crucial role in the detection of spelling errors.

Figure-4: Preprocessing in mBERT model

During the model implementation process, a token-level classification approach was employed. Specifically, each token was assigned to one of two classes:

O – correctly written token;

ERR – token containing a spelling error.

The mBERT tokenizer was utilized during the tokenization process.

Model Training and Testing

The dataset was divided into three subsets: training, validation, and testing datasets. This division enabled the prevention of overfitting and ensured an objective evaluation of the model's performance. The mBERT model was trained using a fine-tuning approach. During the training process, the following hyperparameters were selected:

Table 1: MBERT model parameters

Parametr	Qiymat
Epoch	3-5
Learning rate	2e-5
Batch size	16
Max sequence length	128
Optimizer	AdamW
Loss function	CrossEntropyLoss
Weight decay	0.01

The model was trained for 3–5 epochs, meaning that multiple complete passes over the dataset were performed. During training, the learning rate was set to 2e-5. An excessively large learning rate may negatively affect the stability of the learning process, whereas an overly small value can significantly slow down model training.

The batch size was set to 16, representing the number of samples processed simultaneously by the model. This value provided a balance between computational resource requirements and training stability. The maximum sequence length was defined as 128 tokens, which was sufficient to cover most sentences while maintaining computational efficiency.

The AdamW algorithm was employed as the optimizer during model training. This optimizer is widely used for Transformer-based models and, together with the weight decay mechanism, improves the model's generalization capability. As the loss function, CrossEntropyLoss was selected since the study addressed a token-level binary classification task involving the distinction between correct and erroneous tokens.

Additionally, the weight decay parameter was set to 0.01. This parameter regularizes model weights, reduces overfitting, and enhances the model's ability to generalize to unseen data.

During the testing phase, the model was evaluated using new text samples that had not previously been presented during training. For each token, the model calculated a probability score and assigned a final class label based on a predefined threshold value. If the probability of a token being erroneous exceeded the specified threshold, it was classified as ERR.

```
test_sentence = "Men bugun maktabga bordim va togri javob yozdim"

results = detect_errors_in_sentence(test_sentence)

for r in results:
    print(r)

{'token': 'Men', 'err_probability': 0.0, 'label': 'O'}
{'token': 'bugun', 'err_probability': 0.0023, 'label': 'O'}
{'token': 'maktabga', 'err_probability': 0.9647, 'label': 'ERR'}
{'token': 'bordim', 'err_probability': 0.1379, 'label': 'O'}
{'token': 'va', 'err_probability': 0.0001, 'label': 'O'}
{'token': 'togri', 'err_probability': 0.9998, 'label': 'ERR'}
{'token': 'javob', 'err_probability': 0.0001, 'label': 'O'}
{'token': 'yozdim', 'err_probability': 0.0007, 'label': 'O'}
```

Figure 5. Model test result

The model's ability to operate by considering contextual information demonstrates its superiority over traditional approaches and confirms the effectiveness of deep learning methods in spelling error detection tasks.

Results and Discussion

During the experimental phase, a token-level mBERT-based model was trained and evaluated on a separate test dataset. Four primary evaluation metrics were used to assess model performance: **Accuracy**, **Precision**, **Recall**, and **F1-Score**, which represents the harmonic balance between precision and recall.

In the evaluation of classification models, the concept of a **confusion matrix** plays a central role. It consists of four key values: **True Positive (TP)** – sentences correctly identified by the model as erroneous; **True Negative (TN)** – sentences correctly identified as error-free; **False Positive (FP)** – sentences that were actually correct but incorrectly classified as erroneous by the model; and **False Negative (FN)** – sentences that contained errors but were not detected by the model.

Based on these values, the evaluation metrics are calculated using the following formulas:

Overall **Accuracy** indicates the proportion of all correctly predicted instances:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$$

The **Precision** metric measures the proportion of instances that were actually erroneous among all sentences predicted by the model as containing errors:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

The **Recall** metric represents the proportion of all erroneous sentences that were successfully identified by the model:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

The **F1-Score** is the harmonic mean of the two metrics above and combines the balance between precision and recall into a single evaluation measure:

$$F1 = \frac{2 * \text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

According to the experimental results, the model achieved the following performance on the test dataset:

Figure 6. Results of the Mbert model evaluation

As can be observed from the graph, the model demonstrated high performance across all four evaluation metrics. The Accuracy score achieved the highest value, indicating that the model correctly classified the vast majority of the evaluated sentences.

The Precision score was the highest among all metrics. This result indicates that the model produced very few false positive predictions among the sentences labeled as erroneous. In other words, cases where correct sentences were incorrectly identified as containing errors were minimal.

The Recall score was slightly lower, suggesting that a small portion of erroneous sentences was not detected by the model. In spelling-checking systems, recall is considered particularly important because missing an actual error may be more harmful than incorrectly marking a correct sentence as erroneous. Therefore, future work aims to further improve recall by reducing the threshold value.

The F1-Score remained at a high level, confirming that an acceptable balance between Precision and Recall was maintained. This metric demonstrates that the model operates in a balanced manner rather than favoring a single performance aspect. During the threshold optimization process, various threshold values were tested. The optimal threshold value was selected at the point where the F1-Score reached its maximum value. This threshold has been integrated into the system and is currently applied in the deployment environment.

According to previous studies, BLEU and ROUGE metrics are also widely used in evaluating Natural Language Processing systems. The BLEU metric was originally developed to measure machine translation quality. It evaluates the overlap of n-grams—sequences of consecutive words—between the generated text and a reference text. Therefore, applying BLEU to text generation models, such as mT5, is appropriate. However, using BLEU for mBERT is not suitable because mBERT performs a binary classification task rather than generating text; it only predicts whether an error is present or absent.

Similarly, the ROUGE metric is commonly employed for evaluating text summarization systems. It measures the overlap of n-grams between the reference text and the model output. Like BLEU, ROUGE is designed for generative models, and its application to classification tasks is not methodologically justified.

Therefore, selecting Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score as evaluation metrics for the mBERT model in this study is considered a fully justified decision. In future work, once the

mT5-based correction model is fully integrated, BLEU and ROUGE metrics are planned to be employed for evaluating the quality of generated corrections.

Error analysis

A deeper examination of the test results revealed the specific cases in which the model tends to make errors. Such analysis is important for identifying the weaknesses of the system and determining directions for future improvements.

The observed error cases can be divided into several categories. The first category includes **short and ambiguous words**. Even when spelling errors occur in words consisting of two or three characters, the model may still classify them as correct. This is mainly because short words do not provide sufficient contextual information during the tokenization process.

The second category involves **errors related to language-specific Uzbek characters**. Due to the unique characteristics of the Uzbek alphabet, the model did not always distinguish between letters such as *o* and *g* and their variants written without apostrophe markers. This issue was particularly noticeable when the overall visual form of the word remained relatively unchanged.

The third category consists of **context-based errors**. In cases where a word was misspelled but the overall sentence structure still appeared grammatically correct, the model assigned a relatively low probability to the error. This limitation reflects the constraints of a sentence-level contextual model.

These shortcomings represent natural limitations of the current system implementation. To address them, future work includes enriching the training dataset, introducing more effective token-level error detection mechanisms, and fine-tuning the model using real user-generated data.

The obtained results indicate that the model's high accuracy demonstrates its practical applicability in real-world scenarios.

Conclusion

In this study, an automatic spell-checking model for detecting spelling errors in Uzbek-language texts was developed. Within the scope of the research, a comprehensive dataset was constructed using texts collected from literary works and online sources, and it was enriched with both real and artificially generated errors.

Overall, the proposed approach provides an effective solution for the problem of spelling error detection in the Uzbek language. At the same time, future improvements may include expanding the dataset using real user data and further enhancing the model architecture in order to improve its accuracy and overall performance.

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